

1 **Effect of injectable progestin-only contraceptives, depot medroxyprogesterone**
2 **acetate and norethisterone enanthate, on cytokine production during T cell**
3 **activation.**

4 Injectable DMPA, Cytokines, HIV

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6 Allen T. Matubu¹, Sharon L. Hillier^{2,3}, Leslie A. Meyn², Kevin A. Stoner³, Felix
7 Mhlanga¹, M. Mbizvo¹, A. Maramba⁴, Zvavahera M. Chirenje¹, Sharon L. Achilles^{2,3}

8 *¹University of Zimbabwe -Clinical Trials Research Centre, Department of Obstetrics*
9 *and Gynaecology, Harare, Zimbabwe, ²University of Pittsburgh, School of Medicine,*
10 *Department of Obstetrics, Gynaecology and Reproductive Sciences, Pittsburgh, PA,*
11 *United States, ³Magee-Womens Research Institute, Pittsburgh, PA, United*
12 *States, ⁴University of Zimbabwe Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Department*
13 *of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Harare, Zimbabwe*

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27 **Corresponding Author**

28 *Allen T Matubu, University of Zimbabwe -Clinical Trials Research Centre,*
29 *Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Harare, Zimbabwe, 15 Phillips Ave,*
30 *Belgravia, Harare, Tel: +263773217096, (amatubu@uz-ctrc.org).*

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32 **Problem:** There is paucity of human data about the effects of depot-
33 medroxyprogesterone (DMPA) and norethisterone enanthate (Net-En) use on
34 systemic immune function, which may have implications for reproductive tract
35 infection susceptibility and transmissibility. We sought to evaluate the impact of
36 injectable contraceptive use on T cell responsiveness using T cells exposed *in vivo*
37 and tested *ex vivo*.

38 **Methods:** Peripheral blood mononuclear cells were obtained from healthy, HIV-
39 negative women after 30, 90, and 180-days of DMPA, norethisterone enanthate
40 (Net-En) or copper intrauterine device (Cu-IUD) contraceptive use. Cells were
41 stimulated *ex vivo* with phorbol myristate acetate and ionomycin, stained, and
42 analysed using flow cytometry. Mixed effects linear models were used to evaluate
43 change in proportions of T cells producing IFN γ , TNF α , IL-4 and IL-13.

44 **Results:** Compared to baseline, decreased proportions of IFN γ producing CD4+
45 and CD8+ T cells ($p=.003$, $p=.006$, respectively) and TNF α producing CD4+ and
46 CD8+ T cells ($p=.039$, $p=.034$, respectively) were observed after 180 days of
47 DMPA use. Decreased IL-4 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells ($p=.045$ and
48 $p=.024$ respectively) were noted after 180 days of Net-En use. Decreased IL-4
49 producing CD4+ T cells were observed after 30 days ($p=.035$) and not after 180
50 days of DMPA use ($p=.49$). There were no changes in proportion of T cells
51 producing IL-13 in DMPA users, nor any changes in IFN γ , TNF α and IL-13 in
52 Net-En and Cu-IUD users.

53 **Conclusion:** *In vivo* exposure of CD4+ and CD8+ T cells to typical pharmacologic
54 concentrations of DMPA does not cause broad suppression to stimuli, however
55 depletion of specific cytokine producing T cells may occur after prolonged DMPA
56 use.

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59

60 **Introduction**

61 Use of safe, effective and affordable contraception is key to preventing unwanted
62 pregnancies and associated morbidity and mortality.¹ Injectable contraceptives are
63 increasingly used in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA).² Progestin-only injectable
64 contraceptives, including depot medroxyprogesterone acetate (DMPA), administered
65 as a 150mg/ml intramuscular injection every 3 months, and norethisterone enanthate
66 (Net-En), administered as a 200mg/ml intramuscular injection every 2 months, are
67 both commonly used by women in areas of SSA with high HIV prevalence.³ DMPA
68 and Net-En have different binding affinities to various endogenous steroid
69 receptors.⁴ For instance, medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA), the active ingredient
70 found in DMPA, binds the glucocorticoid receptor (GR) on the order of magnitude of
71 cortisol, a recognized immunosuppressive, and the endogenous ligand for the GR.⁴⁻⁷
72 Norethisterone enanthate (Net-En), has far lower binding affinity for the GR
73 compared to DMPA.^{4,5} These biological differences may result in differential impacts
74 on T cell immune responsiveness in women using DMPA compared to those using
75 Net-En.

76 Published data from both epidemiological and *in vitro* studies have raised concern
77 that DMPA use may be associated with increased risk of HIV acquisition.⁸⁻¹⁴ Multiple
78 *in vitro* studies exploring the immunomodulatory role of DMPA report that DMPA is
79 immunosuppressive.¹⁵⁻²³ A recently conducted randomized clinical trial designed to
80 compare the risk of HIV acquisition in women using DMPA, levonorgestrel
81 contraceptive implants, and copper intrauterine device (Cu-IUD) did not demonstrate
82 differences in HIV acquisition between users of these three contraceptive methods
83 over 18 months of follow up.²⁴ Given the clear and consistent *in vitro* data
84 demonstrating an immunosuppressive effect of DMPA on T-cells, the preponderance
85 of epidemiologic data suggesting a higher relative risk of HIV acquisition associated
86 with DMPA use, and the design of the randomized trial, concern remains. Notably,
87 important *in vivo* factors cannot be mirrored in *in vitro* studies,²¹ including
88 pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, effect of serum hormone binding proteins,
89 duration of immune cell exposure, and innumerable other upstream and downstream
90 factors.

91 Given the well-documented DMPA interaction with the GR, it is plausible that DMPA
92 is immunosuppressive in isolation, and that redundant *in vivo* mechanisms may blunt
93 immunosuppressive effects. We sought to investigate the effect of *in vivo* DMPA and
94 Net-En contraceptive use on T cell production of IFN γ and TNF α , and IL-4 and IL-13,
95 as two representative cytokines associated with T helper type 1(Th1) and T helper
96 type 2 (Th2) responsiveness respectively. We hypothesized that immunosuppressive
97 effects associated with DMPA use, would be observed at steady-state serum MPA
98 concentrations (relatively high) compared to at nadir (low) progestin concentrations
99 that occur immediately prior to next clinical dosing.

100 **Methods**

101 **Study Participants**

102 This sub-study was conducted using samples collected as part of a larger prospective
103 cohort of healthy, reproductive aged Zimbabwean women seeking contraception who
104 enrolled into the Zim CHIC (Zimbabwe Contraceptive Hormone Induced Changes)
105 longitudinal cohort study (ClinicalTrials.gov no: NCT02038335) between February
106 2014 and December 2015. The study recruited healthy, HIV uninfected women aged
107 18-34 who self-selected one of six study-provided contraceptives to initiate and use
108 during 6 months of study participation. This study includes Zim CHIC participants who
109 opted to use DMPA, Net-En, or Cu-IUD. DMPA and Net-En administered on their
110 respective clinical dosing schedules resulted in participants respectively receiving 2
111 doses of DMPA (day 90 and 180) or 3 doses of Net-En (day 60, 120, and 180) during
112 their 6-month study participation. Participants were confirmed to be HIV-1 negative
113 and free of active sexually transmitted infections (HSV-2, *Chlamydia trachomatis* and
114 *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Treponema pallidum* and *Trichomonas vaginalis*), and in the
115 follicular phase of their menstrual cycle at enrollment. Participants were required not
116 to have used DMPA for 10 months nor any other hormonal or intrauterine
117 contraception 30 days preceding enrollment. Detailed descriptions of Zim CHIC study
118 participants have been previously published.^{25,26} This study was approved by the
119 Medical Research Council of Zimbabwe (MRCZ/A.2133) and the University of
120 Pittsburgh (STUDY19050079) Institutional Review Boards. All participants were
121 enrolled at Spilhaus Family Planning Center in Harare, Zimbabwe, and signed
122 informed consent before study participation.

123

124 **Literature search of studies evaluating cytokine responses of T cells exposure**
125 **to MPA**

126 A comprehensive search of all published studies that have investigated the
127 relationship between use of MPA and cytokine production by T cells was conducted
128 in PubMed and Google Scholar databases. The following key words were used as
129 search criteria: injectable DMPA, cytokines, progestin-only injectable contraceptives,
130 DMPA, T cell immunity. Citation searching was also used to further identify articles
131 that could have been missed through the database search. Articles that included at
132 least one of the cytokines in the current study and published in a peer reviewed
133 journal by 31 January 2020 were included.

134 **Blood samples**

135 Serum MPA and norethindrone (NET) concentrations were measured at each
136 study visit using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass
137 spectrometry (UPLC/MS/MS) as previously described²⁵ to assess the serum
138 progestin concentration that PBMCs were exposed to *in vivo*. PBMCs were
139 collected in BD Cell Preparation Tubes (Becton Dickinson and Company, Franklin
140 Lakes, NJ) at enrollment (baseline, prior to initiating contraception), at a steady state
141 dose, and at dose nadir for MPA and NET. Samples collected 30-days following
142 clinical dosing were used to represent steady state, we used the 30-day and 90-day
143 visit samples for steady state in women using DMPA and Net-En respectively.
144 PBMCs collected at the 180-day visits were used to represent nadir dose both for
145 DMPA and Net-En, as these samples were collected immediately prior to next
146 clinical dosing.

147 Following collection, PBMCs were harvested per manufacturer instructions and
148 cryopreserved in 90% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 10% dimethyl
149 sulfoxide (DMSO) (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and stored in liquid nitrogen until
150 analysis.

151 **Frozen PBMC recovery**

152 PBMCs were rapidly thawed using gentle agitation in a 37°C water bath followed by
153 drop-wise addition of pre-warmed culture medium containing 1-part FBS and 9-parts
154 RPMI 1640 with Glutamine (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO). Cells were washed by

155 centrifugation at 500xg for 8 minutes and re-suspended to 1×10^6 cells/ml in culture
156 medium and rested overnight at 37°C in 5% CO₂. Cell viability was determined by
157 staining using 0.4% trypan blue and counting cells on a haemocytometer using a
158 high-power microscope ocular.²⁸ Cell viability after recovery was >95% for all
159 specimens before stimulation, which is comparable to published viability of 95.2%
160 from an optimisation study.²⁹

161

162 **PMA/Ionomycin-induced PBMC stimulation**

163 To achieve broad T cell activation, 50ng/ml PMA and 1µg ionomycin were used
164 following T cell stimulation guidelines.³⁰ PMA was selected because it diffuses
165 through the cell membrane and directly stimulates protein kinases rather than
166 requiring a surface receptor interaction for stimulation. Rested, washed PBMCs
167 reconstituted to 1×10^6 cells/ml were cultured in PMA/ionomycin (Sigma Aldrich, St.
168 Louis, MO) and Anti-Human CD28/49d costimulatory antibody cocktail at final
169 concentration of 50ng/ml. An unstimulated control was included for each participant
170 sample. Protein transport inhibitors, Golgi stop and Golgi plug (BD Biosciences, San
171 Jose, CA), were added to all samples followed by incubation at 37°C in 5% CO₂ for 4
172 hours. The cells were washed, and surface stained using Fixable Viability stain 510
173 (BD Biosciences) as the live/dead discriminator. After a single wash step, cells were
174 stained using BD Biosciences monoclonal antibodies PerCP Mouse Anti-Human
175 CD3, BB515 Mouse Anti-Human CD4, and APC-H7 Mouse Anti-Human CD8, fixed
176 in BD Cytotfix buffer, permeabilised using BD Cytoperm buffer (BD Biosciences) and
177 then stained with PE Mouse Anti-Human CD69, BV421 Rat Anti-Human IL-4, APC
178 Rat Anti-Human IL-13, PE-Cy7 Mouse Anti-Human TNF α , and PE-Cy7 Mouse Anti-
179 Human IFN γ monoclonal antibodies at 4°C in the dark. IFN γ was stained in a
180 separate tube from TNF α , because the two cytokines shared a common
181 fluorochrome. Residual red blood cells were lysed using lysis buffer (Thermo Fisher
182 Scientific, Waltham, MA) following manufacturer instructions. Cells were then
183 washed and re-suspended in 300ul FACS staining buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
184 for acquisition and analysis.

185

186 **Flow Cytometry Analysis**

187 Data were acquired and analysed on a BD FACSCanto II analyser using FASCDIVA
188 software version 6.1.3. Fluorescence Minus One (FMO) and unstimulated controls
189 were used for creating gating templates and all gating and analyses were done in
190 FACSDiva. The flow cytometer was calibrated on each day that samples were
191 processed using Cytometer Setup & Tracking beads kit (BD Biosciences). Single
192 colour compensation controls (CompBead Anti-Mouse Ig, negative control particles
193 set) (BD Biosciences) were applied to each experiment and application settings were
194 used for the study. Flow cytometry gating was reviewed and independently agreed
195 upon by three laboratory scientists for consistency and to minimize bias.

196 **Gating strategy**

197 Figures 1A and 1B show the gating strategy for these analyses. There were 100,000
198 events in the CD3⁺ lymphocyte gate analysed for the frequency of cytokine
199 producing T cells. Only T cells positive for CD69 were considered as cytokine
200 producing cells. From CD69⁺CD4⁺ and CD69⁺CD8⁺ T cells the subset of cells
201 producing each cytokine were determined. The frequency of CD69⁺CD4⁺ and
202 CD69⁺CD8⁺ T cells producing each cytokine was represented as a proportion of
203 CD4⁺ or CD8⁺ T cells. Biexponential scaling was used to show cells falling on the
204 axis.

205 **Statistical Analysis**

206 A previous study found that the median levels of TNF α , IFN γ , and IL-4 producing
207 CD4⁺ cells in healthy adults were 27.3%, 21.6%, and 1.6%, respectively.³¹ A sample
208 size of 28 women in each contraceptive group (DMPA, Net-En, and Cu-IUD) was
209 estimated to have 80% power to detect a 13-33% change in the levels of these
210 cytokine producing CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells after initiation of DMPA or Net-En, based
211 on a paired student's t-test evaluated at the 2-sided .05 significance level.
212 Demographic characteristics of participants in the three contraceptive groups were
213 compared using Kruskal-Wallis and Fisher's Exact tests, where appropriate. Mixed
214 effects linear regression models were used to evaluate changes in proportion of
215 cytokine producing CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells at steady state and at nadir
216 concentrations of DMPA or Net-En, and after 180 days of Cu-IUD use relative to
217 proportions measured at baseline.

218 **Results**

219 PBMCs from 93 participants enrolled in the DMPA (n=28), Net-En (n=33) and
220 Cu-IUD (n=32) arms were included in the analyses. Participants who contracted
221 any sexually transmitted infection during follow up were excluded from analysis.
222 Samples that exhibited bacterial contamination and overgrowth during overnight
223 incubation were also excluded from analyses.

224 The study participants had a median age of 28.0 years. There were no
225 statistically significant differences in baseline demographic characteristics for
226 participants who enrolled in each of the three contraceptive arms (Table 1).
227 Results are presented as change in proportion of cytokine producing CD4+ and
228 CD8+ T cells (Figure 2, Table 2 and Table 3) compared to baseline.

229

230 **Exposure-response MPA and Net-En concentrations**

231 Median serum concentrations measured at the three study visits were used to
232 estimate PBMC exposure concentrations *in vivo* over the six-month study
233 duration. As shown in Table 4, the median MPA and NET concentrations during
234 study participation was 0.415ng/ml (interquartile range (IQR): 0.232-1.042) and
235 1.173ng/ml (IQR: 0.782-1.665) respectively. Table 5 shows exposure-response
236 concentrations from all published studies identified by our literature search methods
237 that reported production of the four cytokines assessed in the present study.

238

239 **DMPA depletes IFN γ and TNF α producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells during**
240 **activation**

241 As shown in Figure 2 and Table 2, DMPA use was associated with a relative
242 decrease in proportion of IFN γ and TNF α producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells after
243 180 days of use (at nadir serum MPA concentration) as compared to baseline
244 (prior to initiating DMPA). There were no significant changes in proportion of
245 IFN γ or TNF α producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells after 30 days of use (at steady
246 state serum MPA concentration). There were no significant changes in
247 proportions of CD4+ and CD8+ T cells producing IFN γ and TNF α relative to
248 baseline in women using Net-En and Cu-IUD at any time point evaluated.

249

250

251 **Net-En depletes IL-4 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells during activation**

252 As shown in Figure 2 and Table 3, Net-En use was associated with a modest
253 decrease in proportion of IL-4 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells (at nadir serum
254 NET concentration) as compared to baseline prior to initiating Net-En. There
255 were no significant changes in proportion of IL-13 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T
256 cells both after 90 days (steady state) and 180 days (nadir state) of Net-En use.
257 DMPA use was associated with decrease in proportion of IL-4 producing CD4+ T
258 cells at 30 days (steady state MPA concentration) after initial injection. There
259 was no change in proportion of IL-13 producing T cells 30 days and 180 days
260 after DMPA use initiation. Non-hormonal Cu-IUD did not alter the proportion of
261 IL-4 and IL-13 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells at any of the evaluated time
262 points. Similar trends were observed when the mean fluorescent intensity was
263 evaluated (data not shown).

264

265 **Discussion**

266 Understanding the immunomodulatory effects of commonly used medications,
267 including DMPA and other hormonal contraceptives, is important in the context of
268 HIV acquisition and transmission. We previously reported that DMPA and Net-En
269 differentially impact T cell responses and expression of immunosuppressive markers
270 following exposure to pharmacologic doses *in vivo*. We also reported that T-cell
271 response to *ex vivo* stimulation is suppressed at steady state MPA concentrations
272 and resolves at nadir concentration suggesting transient immunosuppression.³² The
273 results presented here further our prior work and demonstrate that after 180-days of
274 injectable contraceptive use, at nadir hormone concentrations, physiologically
275 exposed T-cells have depleted cytokine production. Findings from our two studies
276 suggest T-cell related immune system changes that occur in DMPA users and that
277 could impact susceptibility to infections including HIV, consistent with *in vitro* studies
278 demonstrating reduction in T cell release of IFN γ and TNF α following MPA
279 exposure.^{19,20, 21, 32} However, we also demonstrated that physiologic exposure to
280 DMPA did not significantly reduce the proportion of IL-4 and IL-13 producing T cells
281 after six months of use, a finding that differs from published studies of T cells
282 exposed to MPA *in vitro*.^{21,22,33}

283 Following intramuscular injection with 150mg DMPA, serum MPA concentrations rise
284 to ~25ng/ml within days and decline to between 1-9ng/ml over the subsequent 12-
285 week dosing period.^{6,34} Net-En the other progestin-only injectable contraceptive
286 attains peak serum NET levels averaging 11-12ng/ml within 4-7 days of injection.³⁵
287 We collected PBMCs at baseline, day 30 (mean serum MPA concentration of
288 1.303ng/ml defined as steady state), and day 180 (mean serum MPA concentration
289 of 0.279ng/ml defined as nadir state) after DMPA use initiation and, day 90 (mean
290 serum NET concentration of 1.496ng/ml defined as steady state), and day 180
291 (mean serum NET concentration of 0.835ng/ml defined as nadir state) after Net-En
292 use initiation. Immunosuppressive effects of DMPA were observed for IFN γ and
293 TNF α producing T cells only at 180 days and not at 30 days. Production of IL-4 by
294 CD4+ T cells was decreased after 30 days and this change was transient and
295 resolved by 180 days. Data from several published studies have suggested dose
296 dependent MPA inhibition of cytokine production.^{21,22} We observed suppression of
297 cytokine production at nadir DMPA concentrations after six months of exposure. In a
298 recent published review, the authors hypothesized factors that may affect
299 bioavailability of exogenous hormones *in vivo* and suggested that there may be an
300 MPA cut-off below which immunosuppression does not occur.³⁶ Our study
301 demonstrated depleted IFN γ and TNF α T cell responses at serum concentrations as
302 low as 0.279ng/ml, which suggest the effect could occur at even lower hormone
303 concentrations *in vivo*.

304 Our results suggest that duration of DMPA use could be an important factor
305 influencing the immunomodulatory role of DMPA, which has also been
306 hypothesized²¹, furthermore, findings from our study suggest that prolonged
307 physiological exposure of immune cells may enhance DMPA immunosuppressive
308 effect. Women enrolled into the Evidence for Contraceptive Options and HIV
309 Outcomes (ECHO) study were followed for 18 months with DMPA administered at
310 three monthly intervals and the study reported no differences in HIV incidence
311 between women initiating DMPA, LNG-I and Cu-IUD over 18-months use.²⁴ It is
312 plausible that if immunosuppressive effects observed in our study plays any role in
313 HIV infection, the incremental risk would be much lower than the 30% effect that
314 ECHO was powered to detect. Additionally, *in vivo*, immune modulation and
315 biological susceptibility to HIV are likely multifactorial and not exclusively influenced

316 by DMPA. The ECHO study did not rule out biologically plausible DMPA-induced
317 cellular level changes, and in light of consistent data from laboratory studies showing
318 an immunomodulatory role of MPA, further research is needed to understand if these
319 cellular-level changes alter HIV susceptibility which would be important for women
320 living in regions with high HIV incidence and where DMPA is widely used.

321 Subsequent to the publication of the ECHO trial, several authors have similarly
322 discussed the ECHO trial limitations and raised concerns that the ECHO trial results
323 could prematurely halt research on important underlying biological mechanisms.³⁷⁻³⁹

324 Results from our study affirm several findings previously reported from *in vitro*
325 studies, such as reduced production of IFN γ and TNF α by T cells following exposure
326 to MPA.¹⁵⁻²³ One of the key limitations of the published *in vitro* studies is that the
327 hormone concentration and exposure conditions do not closely mimic physiological
328 conditions. Our study aimed to assess the T cell concentration exposures in our
329 study compared to published *in vitro* studies (Table 5) and to mitigate this limitation
330 by using T cells that had been exposed to MPA *in vivo* and then exposing them to a
331 stimulus *ex vivo* and measuring their responsive cytokine production. It is notable
332 that blood sampling in this study was not designed to evaluate T cells obtained at
333 peak *in vivo* serum concentrations of MPA and NET, occurring by median day 2-
334 14 after injection, at which time median serum concentrations for MPA and NET
335 are typically up to 10-fold higher compared to concentrations at day 30.³⁶
336 Furthermore, methods for evaluating cytokine production differ across studies
337 and thus the results are not directly comparable.

338 Cytokines play a critical role in regulating immune response by enabling
339 communication between white blood cells, eliciting chemotaxis (chemokines), and
340 mediating antiviral effects (interferons).⁴⁰ It is logical to suggest that observed *in vitro*
341 changes in the proportion of cytokine producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells could
342 negatively impact immune cell signalling and overall immune response to infection.
343 Nevertheless, the depletion in IFN γ and TNF α producing T cells observed in our
344 study as well as other *in vitro* studies has not been directly linked to increased risk of
345 HIV acquisition.

346

347 No published studies report T cell immune suppression associated with Net-En.
348 Here, we demonstrate that six months of Net-En use was associated with
349 decreased proportion of IL-4 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, suggesting that
350 Net-En may have immunomodulatory effects affecting Th1 and not Th2 cytokine
351 responses. In contrast, we demonstrated that DMPA has immunomodulatory
352 properties that affect both Th1 and Th2 associated responses. Critically, reduced
353 Th1 responses as shown by depleted IFN γ and TNF α raises concerns given the
354 role of IFN γ in mediating cellular immune responses in early viral infection. IFN γ
355 plays a critical role in major histocompatibility complex expression and
356 establishment of anti-viral state for long term control. Equally important is the
357 role of TNF α in driving pro-inflammatory responses and production of acute
358 phase proteins in early infection. Given concordant data from *in vitro* and *in vivo*
359 models reporting depletion of Th1 associated responses in DMPA users, it is
360 plausible to suggest this decrease in Th1 activity may impact HIV-1 acquisition
361 and disease progression.

362 The strengths of this study include that analysis was based on PBMCs from women
363 who had *in vivo* MPA and NET exposures, which addresses some of the limitations
364 of *in vitro* models relating to hormone exposure, serum binding proteins, and other
365 parameters related to pharmacokinetic dynamics. Paired measurements were
366 used to minimize intra-individual variation and objective measurements of
367 hormone concentrations were obtained at each visit to exclude non study hormone
368 use and to understand the median progestin exposure over the six month study
369 period. This study was limited in the number of cytokines assessed, and thus does
370 not cover a broader range of cytokines reported from *in vitro* models. We carefully
371 selected the cytokine panel in this study to represent both Th1 and Th2 responses.
372 We measured cytokines intracellularly, whereas data from most *in vitro* studies is
373 based on measurement of secreted, extracellular cytokines and this could affect
374 comparability of the results. At the steady state time point, although the time from
375 last injection was the same for DMPA users and Net-En users (30 days), the
376 overall duration of exposure to contraceptive hormone at the examined steady
377 state differed for women using DMPA (day 30) compared to Net-En (day 90), which
378 is a noted limitation. We assessed PBMCs over two clinical DMPA dosing cycles,
379 however contracepting reproductive-aged women are often exposed to DMPA for

380 much longer periods. Thus, our observations are limited to the first six months of
381 use and further studies would be required to understand changes beyond this
382 period. Additionally, we acknowledge that PBMC sampling was not conducted at
383 peak serum hormone levels, but rather several weeks after peak hormone
384 exposure at steady state.

385

386 **Conclusion**

387 CD4+ and CD8+ T cells exposed to *in vivo* physiologic concentrations of DMPA
388 produce some cytokines upon stimulation demonstrating immune responsiveness.
389 However, DMPA may cause a decrease in the proportion of specific cytokine
390 producing CD4+ and CD8+ T cells after prolonged *in vivo* exposure. Further
391 research is required to determine whether the observed level of cytokine
392 suppression translates to clinically significant changes in immune responsiveness
393 and risk of acquiring infections.

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407 **References**

- 408 1. UNAIDS. UNAIDS data 2018. July 26, 2018. <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2018/unaids-data-2018> (accessed
409 Aug 6, 2019).
- 410
- 411 2. Jacobstein R, Polis C. Progestin-only contraception: injectables and implants.
412 *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2014;28(6):795– 806
- 413 3. Kharsany AB and Karim QA. HIV Infection and AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa:
414 Current Status, Challenges and Opportunities. *The Open AIDS Journal* 2016;
415 10: 34-48.
- 416 4. Stanczyk FZ, Hapgood JP, Winer S, Mishell DR Jr. Progestogens used in
417 postmenopausal hormone therapy: differences in their pharmacological
418 properties, intracellular actions, and clinical effects. *Endocr Rev.*
419 2013;34(2):171–208. doi:10.1210/er.2012-1008.
- 420 5. Koubovec D, Ronacher K, Stubrud E, Louw A, Hapgood JP. Synthetic
421 progestins used in HRT have different glucocorticoid agonist properties. *Mol*
422 *Cell Endocrinol.* 2005;242:23–32.
- 423 6. Africander D, Verhoog N, Hapgood JP. Molecular mechanisms of steroid
424 receptor-mediated actions by synthetic progestins used in HRT and
425 contraception. *Steroids.* 2011;76:636–652.
- 426 7. Kontula K, Paavonen T, Luukkainen T, Andersson LC. Binding of progestins to
427 the glucocorticoid receptor. Correlation to their glucocorticoid-like effects on in
428 vitro functions of human mononuclear leukocytes. *Biochem Pharmacol.*
429 1983;32:1511–1518.
- 430 8. Morrison CS, Chen PL, Kwok C, Richardson BA, Chipato T, Mugerwa R,
431 Byamugisha J, Padian N, Celentano DD, Salata RA. Hormonal contraception
432 and HIV acquisition: reanalysis using marginal structural modelling. *AIDS*
433 2010;24:1778–1781.
- 434 9. Heffron R, Donnell D, Rees H, Celum C, Mugo N, Were E, de Bruyn G,
435 Nakku-Joloba E, Ngure K, Kiarie J, Coombs RW, Beaten JM. Use of
436 hormonal contraceptives and risk of HIV-1 transmission: a prospective cohort
437 study. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2012;12:19–26.
- 438 10. Baeten JM, Benki S, Chohan V, Lavreys L, McClelland RS, Mandaliya K,
439 Ndinya-Achola JO, Jaoko W, Overbaugh J. Hormonal contraceptive use,

- 440 herpes simplex virus infection, and risk of HIV-1 acquisition among Kenyan
441 women. *AIDS* 2007;21:1771–1777.
- 442 11. Kumwenda NI, Kumwenda J, Kafulafula G, Makanani B, Taulo F, Nkhoma C,
443 Li Q, Taha TE. HIV-1 incidence among women of reproductive age in Malawi.
444 *Int J STD AIDS* 2008;19:339–341.
- 445 12. Plummer FA, Simonsen JN, Cameron DW, et al. Cofactors in male-female
446 sexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus type 1. *Journal of*
447 *Infectious Diseases* 1991; 163:233–239.
- 448 13. Ralph LJ, McCoy SI, Shiu K, Padian NS. Hormonal contraceptive use and
449 women's risk of HIV acquisition: a meta-analysis of observational studies.
450 *Lancet Infectious Diseases* 2015; 15(2):181–189.
- 451 14. Polis CB, Curtis KM, Hannaford PC; Phillips SJ, Chipato T, Kiarie JN,
452 Westreich DJ, Steyn PS. An updated systematic review of epidemiological
453 evidence on hormonal contraceptive methods and HIV acquisition in women.
454 *AIDS* 2016; 30:2665–2683.
- 455 15. Trunova N, Tsai L, Tung S, Schneider E, Harouse J, Gettie A, Simon V,
456 Blanchard J, Cheng-Mayer C. Progestin based contraceptive suppresses
457 cellular immune responses in SHIV-infected rhesus macaques. *Virology* 2006;
458 352:169–177.
- 459 16. Abel K, Rourke T, Lu D, Bost K, McChesney MB, Miller CJ. Abrogation of
460 attenuated lentivirus-induced protection in rhesus macaques by administration
461 of Depo-Provera before intravaginal challenge with simian immunodeficiency
462 virus mac239. *J Infect Dis.* 2004;190:1697–1705.
- 463 17. Genescà M, Li J, Fritts L, Chohan P, Bost K, Rourke T, Blozis SA, McChesney
464 MB, and Miller CJ. Depo-Provera abrogates attenuated lentivirus-induced
465 protection in male rhesus macaques challenged intravenously with pathogenic
466 SIVmac239. *J Med Primatol.* 2007;36(4-5):266–275. doi:10.1111/j.1600-
467 0684.2007.00244.
- 468 18. Veazey RS, Shattock RJ, Pope M, Kirijan JC, Jones J, Hu Q, Ketas T, Marx
469 PA, Klasse PJ, Burton DR, Moore JP. Prevention of virus transmission to
470 macaque monkeys by a vaginally applied monoclonal antibody to HIV-1
471 gp120. *Nat Med.* 2003;9:343–346.
- 472 19. Kleynhans L, Du Plessis N, Black GF, Loxton AG, Kidd M, Van Helden PD,
473 Walzl G, Ronacher K. Medroxyprogesterone Acetate Alters Mycobacterium

- 474 Bovis BCG-Induced Cytokine Production in Peripheral Blood Mononuclear
475 Cells of Contraceptive Users. *PLoS One* 2011; 6(9): e24639.
- 476 20. Kleynhans L, Du Plessis N, Allie N, Jacobs M, Kidd M, van Helden PD, Walzl
477 G, Ronacher K. The contraceptive depot medroxyprogesterone acetate
478 impairs mycobacterial control and inhibits cytokine secretion in mice infected
479 with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Infect Immun*. 2013;81(4):1234–1244.
480 doi:10.1128/IAI.01189-12
- 481 21. Huijbregts RP, Helton ES, Michel KG, Sabbaj S, Richter HE, Goepfert PA, Hel
482 Z. Hormonal Contraception and HIV-1 Infection: Medroxyprogesterone
483 Acetate Suppresses Innate and Adaptive Immune Mechanisms.
484 *Endocrinology* 2013; 154(3):1282–1295.
- 485 22. Huijbregts RP, Michel KG, Hel Z. Effect of progestins on immunity:
486 medroxyprogesterone but not norethisterone or levonorgestrel suppresses the
487 function of T cells and pDCs [published correction appears in *Contraception*.
488 2016 Nov;94(5):578]. *Contraception*. 2014;90(2):123–129.
489 doi:10.1016/j.contraception.2014.02.006
- 490 23. Tomasicchio M, Davids M, Pooran A, et al. The Injectable Contraceptive
491 Medroxyprogesterone Acetate Attenuates *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*-
492 Specific Host Immunity Through the Glucocorticoid Receptor. *J Infect Dis*.
493 2019;219(8):1329–1337. doi:10.1093/infdis/jiy657
- 494 24. Evidence for Contraceptive Options and HIV Outcomes (ECHO) Trial
495 Consortium. HIV incidence among women using intramuscular depot
496 medroxyprogesterone acetate, a copper intrauterine device, or a
497 levonorgestrel implant for contraception: a randomised, multicentre, open-
498 label trial. *Lancet* 2019; Published: June 13, 2019
499 DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)31288-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31288-7).
- 500 25. Achilles SL, Mhlanga FG, Musara P, Poloyac SM, Chirenje ZM, Hillier SL.
501 Misreporting of contraceptive hormone use in clinical research participants.
502 *Contraception*. 2018; 97:346-353.
- 503 26. Matubu A, Hillier SL, Meyn LA, Stoner KA, Mhlanga F, Mbizvo M, Maramba A,
504 Chirenje ZM, Achilles SL. Depot medroxyprogesterone acetate and
505 norethisterone enanthate differentially impact T-cell responses and

- 506 expression of immunosuppressive markers. *Am J Reprod Immunol.* 2019;00:
507 e13210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.13210>
- 508 27. Achilles SL, Meyn LA, Mhlanga FG, Matubu A, Stoner KA, Beamer MA,
509 Chirenje ZM, Hillier SL. Zim CHIC: A cohort study of immune changes in the
510 female genital tract associated with initiation and use of contraceptives. *Am J*
511 *Reprod Immunol.* 2020;00:e13287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.13287>
- 512 28. W. Strober, Trypan blue exclusion test of cell viability, *Curr Protoc Immunol*
513 Appendix 3, Appendix 3B (2001). doi: 10.1002/0471142735.ima03bs21
- 514 29. Hønge BL, Petersen MS, Olesen R, Møller BK, Erikstrup C. Optimizing
515 recovery of frozen human peripheral blood mononuclear cells for flow
516 cytometry. *PLoS One.* 2017;12(11):e0187440. 2017.
517 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0187440
- 518 30. [https://www.biolegend.com/protocols/intracellular-flow-cytometry-staining-](https://www.biolegend.com/protocols/intracellular-flow-cytometry-staining-protocol/4260/)
519 [protocol/4260/](https://www.biolegend.com/protocols/intracellular-flow-cytometry-staining-protocol/4260/) accessed 20 January 2015
- 520 31. Hoffmann F, Albert MH, Arenz S, Bidlingmaier C, Berkowicz N, Sedlacek S,
521 Till H, Pawlita I, Renner ED, Weiss M, Belohradsky. Intracellular T-cell
522 cytokine levels are age-dependent in healthy children and adults. *Eur Cytokine*
523 *Netw.* 2005;16:283–288.
- 524 32. Matubu A, Hillier SL, Meyn LA, Stoner KA, Mhlanga F, Mbizvo M, Maramba,
525 Chirenje ZM, Achilles SL. Depot medroxyprogesterone acetate and
526 norethisterone enanthate differentially impact T-cell responses and
527 expression of immunosuppressive markers. *Am J Reprod Immunol*
528 2019;83(3): <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.1321>
- 529 33. Piccinni M-P, Lombardelli L, Logiodice F, Kullolli O, Maggi E and Barkley MS
530 Medroxyprogesterone Acetate Decreases Th1, Th17, and Increases
531 Th22 Responses via AHR Signaling Which Could Affect Susceptibility to
532 Infections and Inflammatory Disease. *Front. Immunol.* 10:642. doi:
533 0.3389/fimmu.2019.00642
- 534 34. Nanda K, Amaral E, Hays M, Viscola MA, Mehta N, Bahamondes L.
535 Pharmacokinetic interactions between depot medroxyprogesterone acetate
536 and combination antiretroviral therapy. *Fertility and sterility.* 2008; 90:965–
537 971.
- 538 35. Gregoire A.T and Richard PB. Contraceptive Steroids: Pharmacology and
539 Safety. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-9313-2>

- 540 36. Hapgood JP, Kaushic C, Hel Z. Hormonal Contraception and HIV-1
541 Acquisition: Biological Mechanisms. *Endocr Rev.* 2018;39(1):36-78.
542 doi:10.1210/er.2017-00103
- 543 37. Hapgood JP. Is the Injectable Contraceptive Depo-Medroxyprogesterone
544 Acetate (DMPA-IM) Associated with an Increased Risk for HIV Acquisition?
545 The Jury Is Still Out. *AIDS Research and Human Retroviruses* 2020; 36 (5):
546 DOI: 10.1089/aid.2019.0228
- 547 38. Marrazzo J, Achilles SL, Balkus JE, Noguchi L. ECHO: context and
548 limitations. Response to “HIV incidence among women using intramuscular
549 depot medroxyprogesterone acetate, a copper intrauterine device, or a
550 levonorgestrel implant for contraception: a randomized, multicenter, open-
551 label trial”. *Lancet.* 2020 Feb;395(10222):e23. doi: 10.1016/S0140-
552 6736(19)33112-5.
- 553 39. Beacroft L, Smith JA, Hallett TB. What impact could DMPA use have had in
554 South Africa and how might its continued use affect the future of the HIV
555 epidemic? *J Int AIDS Soc.* 2019;22(11):e25414. doi:10.1002/jia2.2541440.
- 556 40. Kleiner G, Marcuzzi A, Zanin V, Monasta L, and Zauli G. Cytokine Levels in
557 the Serum of Healthy Subjects. *Mediators of Inflammation* 2013.
558 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/434010>

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570 **Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population**

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Characteristic	DMPA (n=28)	Net-En (n=33)	Cu-IUD (n=32)	p-value
Age, years	27.5 (23.0, 30.0)	28.0 (24.5, 30.0)	29.0 (26.0, 32.0)	.35*
Body mass index, kg/m ²	22.9 (21.3, 25.1)	23.0 (21.1, 28.5)	25.8 (22.9, 29.4)	.06*
Marital status				.48†
Never married	0	1 (3.0)	3 (9.4)	
Married	24 (85.7)	29 (87.9)	22 (68.8)	
Divorced	3 (10.7)	2 (6.1)	5 (15.6)	
Separated	1 (3.6)	1 (3.0)	2 (6.3)	
Partner status				.13†
No current partner	1 (3.6)	0	2 (6.3)	
Lives with partner	24 (84.7)	29 (87.9)	21 (65.6)	
Does not live with partner	3 (10.7)	4 (12.1)	9 (28.1)	
Educational attainment				.27†
Primary	5 (17.9)	2 (6.1)	3 (9.4)	
Secondary	23 (82.1)	30 (90.9)	26 (81.3)	
Tertiary	0	1 (3.0)	3 (9.4)	

572 Data presented as median (IQR) or n (%)

573 * P-value from Kruskal-Wallis test

574 † P-value from Fisher's exact test

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585 **Table 2: Proportion of CD4+ IFN γ +, CD8+ IFN γ +, CD4+TNF α +, and CD8+ TNF α + cells**
 586 **at steady state and nadir serum progestin concentrations after initiation and use of**
 587 **contraception compared to baseline**

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	Parameter	Baseline	Steady state (day 30)	p-value*	Nadir (day 180)	p-value*
DMPA	CD4+ IFN γ +	17.1 (9.1)	16.5 (7.1)	.630	14.6 (6.8)	.003
	CD8+ IFN γ +	66.1 (20.3)	59.3 (16.5)	.263	55.6 (20.1)	.006
	CD4+ TNF α +	57.3 (14.1)	58.5 (11.1)	.531	53.0 (14.3)	.039
	CD8+ TNF α +	59.6 (21.7)	59.3 (16.0)	.632	54.5 (19.6)	.034
		Baseline	Steady state (day 90)	p-value*	Nadir (day 180)	p-value*
Net-En	CD4+ IFN γ +	17.5 (7.6)	16.3 (6.5)	.279	16.8 (6.9)	.528
	CD8+ IFN γ +	61.5 (17.3)	61.6 (16.5)	.667	62.2 (15.4)	.988
	CD4+ TNF α +	56.2 (11.3)	56.4 (12.6)	.890	56.2 (11.9)	.773
	CD8+ TNF α +	58.8 (16.2)	59.7 (15.0)	.869	59.9 (14.2)	.965
		Baseline			Day 180	p-value*
CU-IUD	CD4+ IFN γ +	16.7 (6.4)			16.9 (6.8)	.924
	CD8+ IFN γ +	68.9 (13.5)			66.4 (16.4)	.678
	CD4+ TNF α +	58.7 (12.5)			59.9 (12.6)	.308
	CD8+ TNF α +	69.3 (13.2)			68.2 (12.7)	.562

589 Data are presented as mean (standard deviation)

590 * p-value from mixed effects linear regression comparing proportion of IFN γ and TNF α
 591 secreting CD4 and CD8 T cells obtained from women at baseline (prior to contraceptive
 592 initiation) to cells collected at steady state clinical dosing (day 30 for DMPA or day 90
 593 for Net-En) and to a nadir dose (day 180) following contraceptive initiation and use

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602 **Table 3: Proportion of CD4+IL13+, CD8+IL13+, CD4+IL4+, and CD8+IL4+ cells at**
 603 **steady state and nadir serum progestin concentrations after initiation and use of**
 604 **contraception compared to baseline.**

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	Parameter	Baseline	Steady state (day 30)	p-value*	Nadir (day 180)	p-value*
DMPA						
	CD4+IL13+	2.5 (1.2)	2.6 (1.1)	.533	2.3 (1.2)	.136
	CD8+ IL13+	1.2 (0.9)	1.3 (0.7)	.166	1.1 (0.6)	.397
	CD4+ IL4+	4.9 (2.9)	3.9 (2.3)	.035	4.5 (4.7)	.493
	CD8+ IL4+	2.8 (2.7)	3.0 (5.1)	.872	2.8 (3.9)	.920
		Baseline	Steady state (day 90)	p-value*	Nadir (day 180)	p-value*
Net-En						
	CD4+IL13+	2.8 (1.5)	2.8 (1.4)	.899	2.8 (1.6)	.830
	CD8+ IL13+	1.6 (1.4)	1.5 (1.1)	.225	1.5 (1.4)	.691
	CD4+ IL4+	5.7 (5.2)	5.0 (3.6)	.401	4.5 (3.3)	.045
	CD8+ IL4+	3.2 (3.1)	2.7 (2.9)	.590	2.2 (1.9)	.024
		Baseline			180 days	p-value*
Cu-IUD						
	CD4+IL13+	2.6 (1.5)			2.8 (1.7)	.307
	CD8+ IL13+	1.5 (1.4)			1.4 (1.0)	.092
	CD4+ IL4+	4.9 (3.5)			4.7 (3.2)	.350
	CD8+ IL4+	2.6 (2.4)			2.5 (2.1)	.272

606 Data are presented as mean (standard deviation)

607 * p-value from mixed effects linear regression comparing proportion of IL-4 and IL-13
 608 secreting CD4 and CD8 T cells obtained from women at baseline (prior to contraceptive
 609 initiation) to cells collected at steady state clinical dosing (day 30 for DMPA or day 90
 610 for Net-En) and to a nadir dose (day 180) following contraceptive initiation and use
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618 **Table 4: Median MPA and NET serum concentrations measured 30-, 90- and 180-days**
 619 **after initiation and continuous use**

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	MPA (ng/ml)				NET ng/ml			
	Day 30	Day 90	Day 180	All Visits	Day 30	Day 90	Day 180	All Visits
min value	0.27	BLQ	0.07	BLQ	0.26	0.46	0.216	0.216
max value	3.308	0.702	0.592	3.308	3.43	2.66	2.49	3.43
IQR 25%	1.01	0.187	0.18	0.232	0.801	1.04	0.562	0.782
median	1.303	0.302	0.279	0.415	1.289	1.496	0.835	1.173
IQR 75%	1.631	0.485	0.368	1.042	1.724	1.818	1.179	1.665

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622 **MPA** – medroxyprogesterone acetate, **IQR** – interquartile range, **NET**- norethisterone623 **BLQ** - Below the limit of quantification (<0.025ng/ml)

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638 **Table 5: Summary of primary findings from published studies showing effect of DMPA**
 639 **on PBMCs and CD3+ T cell production of IL13, IL4, TNF α and IFN γ**

Study	Type of cells assessed	MPA exposure-response concentrations*	Primary Findings
Kleynhans <i>et al</i> 2011 ¹⁹	Human PBMCs (<i>in vitro</i>)	3.4ng/ml, 15.4ng/ml, 96.3ng/ml [8.8nM, 40nM, 250nM]	1L-4 ↓ IL-13 ↓ TNF- α ↓ IFN-Y ↓
Huijbregts <i>et al</i> 2013 ²¹	Human PBMCs and purified CD3+ cells (<i>in vitro</i>)	38.65ng/ml [100nM]	1L-4 ↓ IL-13 ↓ TNF- α ↓ IFN-Y ↓
Huijbregts <i>et al</i> 2014 ²²	Human PBMCs (<i>in vitro</i>)	3.86ng/ml [10nM]	1L-4 ↓ IL-13 ↓ TNF- α ↔ IFN-Y ↓
Tomasicchio <i>et al</i> 2019 ²³	Human PBMCs (<i>in vitro</i>)	38.65ng/ml [100nM]	1L-13 ↔ TNF- α ↔ IFN-Y ↓
Piccinni <i>et al</i> 2019 ³²	CD4+ Clones (<i>in vitro</i>)	0.02ng/ml, 0.2ng/ml, 2ng/ml	1L-4 ↔ IL-13 ↓ TNF- α ↓ IFN-Y ↓
Kleynhans <i>et al</i> 2013 ²⁰	Mouse serum (<i>in vivo</i>)	27.42ng/ml, 31.6ng/ml, 29.42ng/ml	TNF- α ↓ IFN-Y ↓
Current Study	Human CD4 and CD8 T cells (<i>in vivo</i>)	0.415ng/ml (0.232 - 1.042)	1L-4 ↔ IL-13 ↔ TNF- α ↓ IFN-Y ↓

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641 **PBMC**- peripheral blood mononuclear cells; ↓ depicts statistically significant decrease in
 642 cytokine producing T cells; ↔ depicts no change in cytokine producing T cells

643 * All concentrations converted to ng/ml for direct comparison. Units of measurement as
 644 reported in original publication are included in brackets [], () depicts interquartile range.

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657 **Figure 1. Flow cytometry gating strategy.**

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662 **Figure 2. Impact of DMPA, Net-En and Cu-IUD on mean change of CD4+ and CD8+ T**
 663 **cells secreting TNF α , IFN γ , IL-4, and IL-13 compared to baseline**

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673 **Figure 1. Gating strategy demonstrated with representative flow cytometry plots**

674 PBMCs isolated from healthy HIV negative women initiating DMPA, Net-En or Cu-IUD
 675 contraception were incubated in 50ng/ul PMA/ionomycin and Anti-Human CD28/49d
 676 antibody cocktail for 4 hours in the presence of a protein transport inhibitor containing
 677 brefeldin A and monensin. Cells were stained for surface identifier markers, fixed,
 678 permeabilised and stained for intracellular cytokines, IL-4, IL-13, IFN γ and TNF α using
 679 Becton Dickinson fluorochrome conjugated antibodies. Flowcytometric analysis was
 680 performed using a BD FACSCanto II Cytometer. Figure 1A and 1B shows the gating strategy
 681 for IL-4, IL-13, TNF- α and IFN γ respectively. SSC/FSC represents the distribution of all cells
 682 in the light scatter based on size and intracellular composition. The SSC-H/SSC-W plot was
 683 used to identify lymphocytes and to exclude doublet cells from the analysis. SSC/CD3
 684 PerCP was used to cluster all CD3+ cells and further SSC gates to identify CD3+CD69+
 685 (activated T-cells). CD4+ and CD8+ cells positive for intracellular staining of each of the four
 686 cytokines were gated from activated T-cells (CD3+CD69+). Biexponential scaling was used
 687 for visualization of cells falling on the axis.

688 **DMPA** – depot medroxyprogesterone acetate; **Net-En** – norethisterone enanthate; **Cu-IUD** –
 689 copper T380A intrauterine device; **IL-4** – interleukin 4; **IL-13** – interleukin 13; **IFN γ** –
 690 interferon gamma; **TNF α** – tumour necrosis factor alpha; **PBMC** – peripheral blood
 691 mononuclear cells; **PMA** – phorbol myristate acetate; **SSC** – side scatter; **FSC** – forward
 692 scatter.

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695 **Figure 2. Mean change in CD4+ and CD8+ T cells producing TNF α , IFN γ , IL-4, and IL-
 696 13 after contraceptive initiation and use**

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698 PBMCs isolated from women using DMPA, Net-En, and Cu-IUD were stimulated *in vitro* to
 699 assess the cytokine production by CD4+ and CD8+ T cells. PBMCs were collected prior to
 700 first contraceptive administration(baseline), during ^ssteady state drug concentration, and at
 701 ⁿnadir drug concentration for women using DMPA and Net-En. For women using Cu-IUD,
 702 PBMCs were collected at baseline and after 180 days use. Mean change in CD4+ and CD8+
 703 T-cells producing TNF α (**A**), IFN γ (**B**), IL-4 (**C**), and IL-13 (**D**) were evaluated. Mixed linear
 704 models were used to calculate p-values when comparing baseline to follow-up.

705 ^s – For DMPA, defined as 30 days after first injection (mean serum MPA concentration =
 706 1.303ng/ml); For Net-En, defined as 90 days after first injection (mean serum NET
 707 concentration = 1.496ng/ml)

708 ⁿ – defined as immediately prior to next clinical injectable contraceptive dosing 180 days
 709 after first injection. Mean serum concentrations = 0.279ng/ml and 0.835ng/ml for MPA and
 710 NET respectively.

711 **DMPA** – depot medroxyprogesterone acetate; **Net-En** – norethisterone enanthate; **Cu-IUD** –
 712 copper T380A intrauterine device; **IL-4** – interleukin 4; **IL-13** – interleukin 13; **IFN γ** –
 713 interferon gamma; **TNF α** – tumour necrosis factor alpha; **PBMC** – peripheral blood
 714 mononuclear cells; **PMA** – phorbol myristate acetate; **MPA** – medroxyprogesterone acetate;
 715 **NET** – norethisterone

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